

Research Report 2 - Group 29

Digital Methods & Information Analytics

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Course Instructor(s): Stijn Peeters

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What is the impact of cookie settings?

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Yes

1. Introduction

As the use of the Internet grows everyday with more and more users joining the network and navigating the web space, attention towards the privacy and personal data we share online is frequently overlooked. Visiting a new website and tapping on a cookie banner has become part of everyday users activities online of which the consequences are too often neglected or not even known. However, the rise of privacy concerns over “the increasing trend of third-party websites recording and analysing users’ browsing activities across unrelated first-party websites” (Mayer and Mitchell 2012) has incentivised users to pay more attention to these messages. Today any person browsing the web is under constant monitoring from entities who track navigation patterns of users (Yu et al. 2016).

Laws such as the EU’s GDPR try to establish rules for the processing of personal data by companies and public authorities, such as “making consent for nonessential processing a precondition to entering into an agreement” (Davies 2016). However, those rules can create a misconception that companies cannot track users in any form, which is not the case as there are strictly necessary exemptions” that the user cannot deny (Iubenda 2018).

E-commerce websites specifically are known for using session cookies to hold items in the user cart.

The banners thus only promote the idea that the user has full control over their tracking while most places will track out of necessity. As well, many of the banners make users manually opt-out, but this process can be confusing as a study demonstrated “88% of users understood that the page related to online advertising and opting out, but only 11% correctly responded” (Mayer and Mitchell 2012). A user can choose to limit the amount of tracking but never fully eliminate it. As well the opt-out of cookies is always done manually The Web has “become an ecosystem in which users, site-owners, network providers and trackers coexist” (Yu et al. 2016). The collection of user information has unfortunately been normalised for websites, only limited by how much of it the user prefers to be shared. To whom that data goes and how many companies it is given to thus becomes the underlying fear, since it is impossible to know how the data collected through cookies will be employed by tracking companies (Hu et al. 2006).

2. Question

This report, therefore, is focused on investigating the research question: “How does the tracker ecosystem change depending on the cookie preference settings on e-commerce

websites?”.

The link between cookie settings and trackers becomes ever more so interesting when considering what media scholars call *the user imaginaries*. This concept refers to collective beliefs, expectations, and hopes that users may develop when engaging with a technology, and it is thought by academics to have quite the effect on the projection and creation of a plethora of sociotechnical ensembles (Tidwell and Tidwell 2018). In this particular stance, these imaginaries translate into a discrepancy between what the users expect the cookie settings to establish, in terms of their data privacy, in comparison to what they actually do and their real effects on the tracker ecosystem. As a study conducted by Canadian researchers on the user perception and misconception of cookies showcases, an overwhelming majority of internet users assume that denying all cookies will ensure the maximum level of protection against trackers, many believing that the terms “cookies” and “trackers” are interchangeable (Ha et al. 2006). The participants to this study who had a non-technical background also reported that they “found it hard to grasp the idea of what cookies did, and what information was stored/transmitted” (Ha et al. 2006), thus the confusion is only a natural outcome of the disinformation and lack of knowledge on this topic of the general public.

This also ties back into the environment of expected use, which according to Light, Burgess, and Duguay (2018) represents a way for researchers to understand “how an app’s designers, developers, publishers and owners expect users to receive and integrate into their technology usage practices”. However, when it comes to cookie settings and trackers, as touched upon in the Introduction of this paper, the way in which websites in general frame the privacy options of users and the ways in which these mechanisms operate in reality is not in accordance. Computer scientists warn that even effective cookie management tools do not necessarily diminish the persistent data privacy issues (Ha et al. 2006).

Considering the tensions between the ways in which cookie preference settings are framed on e-commerce websites and what users expect them to do, this research aims to explore and highlight these differences; in an attempt to mostly educate users on what exactly their data protection options are when engaging with these widely used websites.

3. Method

In order to answer the research question we are combining three different but related methodological approaches. Firstly, we are using the *tracker studies* method which

represents a “qualitative exploration of tracking practices” (Bounegru 2019). In this way, we are making use of the network analysis with the aim to map out how the tracker ecosystem transforms depending on distinct cookie settings on e-commerce websites, as illustrated in the 3 case-studies that are examined in this report.

The second method draws on from what Helmond (2017) calls a *website ecology* approach, which is deeply rooted in the relations between websites, users and third-party services, while focusing on the larger techno-commercial configurations which websites are part of. Another important facility of this methodological approach is that it enables the researchers to have a better comprehension of the dynamics between websites and third-parties, as Helmond (2017) underlines they are intertwined not only through user behaviour but also due to data connections created by trackers.

We selected a number of 9 e-commerce websites as follows: *Alibaba.com*, *Amazon.nl*, *Amazon.com*, *Ebay.com*, *Bol.com*, *Etsy.com*, *Wish.com*, *Marktplaats.nl*, *Zalando.nl*. Our choices were driven by our interest to investigate different markets, therefore we are researching American, European and Chinese e-commerce websites. This is even more interesting to examine when we consider the GDPR laws of the European Union and their perceived strictness when it comes to matters of data protection and privacy in comparison to other international legislation on this topic. This is also the reason why we opted for studying both *Amazon.nl* and *Amazon.com*, as we were curious to find out if the GDPR legislation makes a considerable impact on the tracker ecosystem of the European version, in contrast to the American one.

The 3 case studies are represented by the 3 options of cookie settings which are “**accept all cookies**”, “**accept only preferential (mandatory) cookies**”, “**deny all cookies**”. On 3 out of the 9 researched e-commerce websites – *Etsy.com*, *Wish.com*, *Zalando.nl* – there was no “**deny all cookies**” option, hence we were constrained to only 2 case studies for these websites. In the background we were running a tracking methodological tool called BrightBeam, which identifies almost all known first and third-party trackers on the accessed websites.

After selecting the cookie setting preference, we began to interact with the website. The reason behind this decision is that most trackers usually start operating after user engagement. Due to this factor and in order to minimise differences between our 3 case-studies, we also repurposed the *walkthrough method*. Originally, this method is based on interacting with an app’s or website’s interface in order to examine its technological

mechanisms (Light, Burgess, and Duguay 2018). Although we are not particularly interested in the interface affordances of the selected e-commerce websites, this method does provide us with the concept of an operationalised and systemised engagement process, as we are taking the same steps while “walking through” these 9 e-commerce websites regardless of the set cookie preference.

Thus, our method begins with a keyword search, “phone case”, as this is one product found on all examined websites. The next step is to click on the first recommended item, for each cookie setting. In all cases but two these items were the same.

Using the trackers captured by BrightBeam in the meantime, we uploaded the network to Gephi, on which we ran the ForceAtlas2 algorithm for a more optimum visualisation, as well as a community detection algorithm which results in a modularity score and filtered the node colours by *tracker_type*, to highlight the kinds of trackers identified. This process resulted in three networks, one for each case study, which will then be employed in a comparative analysis.

From a more quantitative perspective, we also devised a bar chart making use of the data provided by BrightBeam. This second type of data visualisation aims to emphasise the ways in which the number and type of trackers change depending on the cookie settings, in a manner that is more feasible for interpretation and which provides better context for the network analysis.

Fig. 1- Trackers graph visualisation (colours represent tracker type)

4. Analysis

The three network graphs (Fig. 2,3 and 4) representing trackers on the three possible cookie settings have resulted in a set of interesting findings.

Accepting **all cookies** on the selected websites has resulted in all websites being interconnected with each other through trackers (Fig 2). However, this did not turn out to be the case when only accepting **preferential and/or mandatory cookies**. While Etsy, Marktplaats, Amazon and Alibaba did not share any of their trackers with the other websites, Etsy and Marktplaats were the only ones that did not have any trackers at all (Fig 3).

Rejecting all cookies has similarly resulted in Etsy having no trackers attached to its website, however, what is interesting here is that the no cookie setting has resulted in Marktplaats gaining two trackers: Google Analytics and Threat Metrix (Fig 4). Thus, while accepting all cookies connects all websites through trackers and only accepting essential cookies leads to fewer websites interconnected with each other through trackers, the rejecting all cookies setting has shown to add two additional trackers.

Accepting **all cookies** on the websites has showcased that Marktplaats and Alibaba have the most trackers compared to the rest of the websites and that the majority of their trackers are interconnected with each other (Fig 2). Once the cookie setting was changed to **preferential and/or mandatory cookies**, Marktplaats immediately lost all of their trackers while Alibaba was left with only one tracker named MarkMonitor. Furthermore, the website with the most trackers became Ebay, sharing the tracker Google Tag Manager with Bol and Zalando and the tracker DoubleClick with Wish (Fig 3). Similarly, Ebay remained as the website with the most trackers when **rejecting all cookies** and also shares the tracker Google Tag Manager with Bol, but differentiates from the other cookie settings as it now uses the tracker Google AdSense on Marktplaats (Fig 4). The most intriguing aspect is that Bol – a Dutch website - shares its only tracker with US-based company Ebay, although data protection legislation widely varies. In other words, we can say that cookie settings do affect the amount and type of trackers used on various websites. Moreover, choosing to accept less cookies does indeed result in fewer trackers; however, choosing to reject all cookies does not necessarily result in no tracking on the websites.

The case of Amazon.com and Amazon.nl is another slightly different example of how trackers can differ depending on the cookie setting. The network graph has shown that Amazon.nl and Amazon.com are interconnected with only one tracker; **Accept all or essential cookies** setting uses the Amazon Advertising tracker (Fig 2 and 3), while **reject all cookies** setting uses the Amazon Associates tracker (Fig 4). In this particular case, it

becomes clear that accepting all or essential cookies does not result in more or less tracking; however, rejecting all cookies still does not lead to complete absence of tracking.

Fig. 2 - Network graph representing trackers on “accept all cookies” setting

Fig. 3 - Network graph representing trackers on “accept preferential/mandatory cookies” setting

Fig. 4 - Network graph representing trackers on “deny all cookies” setting

The idea that **accepting all cookies** lead to maximum tracking, **essential/preferential cookies** lead to minimised tracking and **denying all cookies** lead to complete absence of tracking seems to be a common understanding among Internet users. However, the three network graphs (Fig. 2,3 and 4) discussed above and the column chart (Fig. 1) indicate otherwise.

As shown in figure 1, there is a significant difference between the three cookies settings and the number of trackers per tracker category. **Accept all cookies** setting tends to have a higher number of trackers in all of the tracker categories. The biggest difference appears to be the most noticeable in advertising trackers. **Accepting all cookies** has resulted in 76 advertising trackers, while both **preferential** and **no cookies** setting each had 13 advertising trackers. While the rest of the tracker categories tend to follow the most-to-least pattern, what seems to be the most interesting takeaway is the similarity between the **preferential and/or essential and no cookie** settings. These settings share the same amount of trackers in 3 out of 5 tracker categories. The user imaginaries that denying all cookies results in complete absence of tracking in comparison to the other two cookie settings is therefore disproved. However, it does confirm the idea that accepting all cookies leads to maximised tracking.

5. Discussion

The analysis of the trackers detected by Brightbeam - through the visual analysis of the two networks and the graph - highlighted several findings worth of more in-depth discussion.

As a result of the Cookie Law, every website should implement a cookie policy and allow the user to make an informed decision about their consent (Iubenda n.d.). Out of the walkthrough implemented for this paper, it was evident that not all websites provided the user with the possibility to make a choice about the data they wanted to share with the publishers and the third-parties online. Indeed, not all the selected e-commerce platforms allowed the user to disable **all cookies** settings, resulting in their exclusion from the third case study (Fig.4). The Cookie Law, moreover, does not refer only to cookies, which are identified by Bounegru (2019) as one of the different web tracking elements, but to all tracking devices in general. This should imply that the user has the possibility of not getting tracked by a website when navigating it.

However, it is shown by the three networks that disabling the cookies' settings on a website does not automatically mean not being tracked, both by first-party and third-party trackers. This goes against not only the Cookie Law, but also common imaginaries around cookies settings online. Cookies are often demonised by users in a misconception of their role as "used to transmit viruses" or, more generally, as the biggest infringement of privacy online (Ha et al. 2006). However, from the analysis conducted, it resulted that cookies are not the only threat to personal data on the web, and denying their usage by websites does not necessarily mean not being tracked, both by the website itself and by external companies (Fig.4).

More interesting findings resulted from a more extensive investigation of the trackers' profiles detected by Brightbeam.

First of all, a high presence of third-party trackers was identified both in the "**preferential cookies settings**" and the "**deny all cookies settings**" networks. Moreover, as shown in the graph, most of them were trackers labelled as "advertising", which suits the business model of the e-commerce websites taken under scrutiny. Yet, it is not clear why a user is still tracked by third parties when consent is plainly denied, considering also that there is not much difference in the trackers' number when accepting only essential cookies compared to when disabling all of them.

Google Tag Manager, Google Analytics and DoubleClicks were the trackers connected to most websites, in all three networks. These trackers are generally used to improve the performance of a website, both in terms of general analytics, advertising and campaigning, and as they are widely employed by different websites it is not surprising to notice their presence on e-commerce websites (Bounegru 2019). Here, however, the question is again whether they should track the user even when consent is explicitly denied.

It is also interesting that Amazon, both the US-based website and the Dutch one, has no external tracker connected to its websites in all three networks. As this may appear as a “cleaner” tracking practice, it is also useful to remember that Amazon is one of the biggest e-commerce platforms that could use a more private handling of the data collected and that can economically afford a first-party extended tracking infrastructure, of which the user is still little informed.

Among the trackers detected when accepting all cookies, some appeared of dubious nature. Trackers like Sales Force, the Digital Windows and Trade Desk - connected to websites like Marktplats or Etsy - perform behavioural targeting, a tracking technique that has been raising several concerns (Carrascosa et al. 2015). Salesforce, for example, claims to make “detailed” user profiles (Sales Force n.d.), while Trade Desk brags about being able to reach users across their devices and for the entire user journey (Trade Desk n.d.). This invasive collection of data builds the imaginary which is then traded by these companies to the websites that rely on them for tracking, with the illusion of selling the ability to know everything about their customers. Nevertheless, this imaginary clashes with the one that is instead presented to the users on the websites themselves, which gives them the illusion of having an actual choice on their privacy and data.

Finally, the idea of following their audience, “no matter where they are” (Sales Force n.d.), in the strenuous attempt of monetizing it, together with the high presence of advertising trackers, furtherly highlights how audience construction and monetisation are now the first revenue streams for ecommerce websites, being today “distributed across an increasingly large number of interdependent actors” (Bounegru 2019, 152).

6. Conclusion

The aim of this paper was to investigate the impact of cookie preference settings on the tracking environment of 9 e-commerce websites within Europe, America and China.

This research has confirmed the user assumption that accepting all cookies leads to an increase in user tracking. At the same time, it has also highlighted the realities of tracking practices online: even when all cookies are denied users data is still acquired by third party trackers whose usage lacks transparency. Our findings, thus, make way for relevant discussions on topics such as data handling and privacy concerns. As a result, it was evident that the user consent on these websites is not directly related to the number of trackers detected.

Further research could look at a larger sample and conduct a more detailed comparative analysis on the trackers' place of origin and aim. Another limitation worth noting is the fact that not enough information was available when it came to the type of data shared with third-party trackers. In relation to this, more professional knowledge of the legal framework might have positively impacted the quality of this paper, therefore it is also recommended for future academic inquiry.

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